

Traumatic Renal Injury in A Horseshoe Kidney: Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Horseshoe kidney (HSK) is the most common congenital renal fusion anomaly, with an annual incidence of 1 case per 500 newborns. While the exact etiologic mechanism remains unknown, its presence predisposes the kidney to traumatic injury; therefore, a proper diagnostic approach is essential for selecting the appropriate definitive treatment.

OBJECTIVE: To describe a case of renal trauma in a patient with a horseshoe kidney.

CLINICAL CASE: A 30-year-old male patient was admitted to the emergency department after being struck by a motor vehicle, with unknown trauma kinematics. The approach was conducted according to the Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) guidelines. Computed tomography (CT) documented bilateral renal trauma in a patient with a horseshoe kidney.

CONCLUSIONS: The prevalence of renal trauma in patients with horseshoe kidneys is limited due to the low prevalence of this anomaly. Consequently, accurate radiological diagnosis and appropriate clinical monitoring are vital when making correct therapeutic decisions.

KEYWORDS: renal trauma, horseshoe kidney, renal ectopia, nephrectomy

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BACKGROUND

Horseshoe kidney (HSK) is the most common congenital renal fusion anomaly, with an annual incidence of 1 case per 500 newborns ⁽¹⁾. It was first described in 1522 by Jacopo Berengario da Carpi, who identified the anomaly during autopsies as the fusion of both renal units across the midline ⁽²⁾. The three most common anatomical abnormalities consist of ectopia, malrotation, and vascular changes ⁽³⁾. In 90% of cases, both kidneys are fused at their lower poles, creating an isthmus (giving it its characteristic U-shape) composed of functional parenchyma with its own blood supply, fibrous tissue, or a combination of both ⁽⁴⁾.

During embryogenesis, two events may contribute to the development of HSK: first, an uncoordinated interaction

between the ureteric bud and the metanephric blastema between the 4th and 11th weeks of gestation; and second, an alteration in the relocation process of the metanephros between the 6th and 9th weeks of gestation ⁽¹⁾. Nonetheless, the differences in renal anatomy, histology, and vasculature observed in HSK variants suggest that multiple mechanisms are involved in renal fusion.

A common theory of HSK development focuses on aberrant cell migration across the sagittal plane, resulting in renal fusion. This may also explain the different compositions of the HSK isthmus, whether it is predominantly composed of renal parenchyma (up to 85% of cases) or fibrous tissue ⁽⁵⁾. Altered cellular signaling from the abdominal aorta during the initial ascent of the left and right metanephros may cause

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divergent cell migration and renal fusion ⁽⁶⁾. Although few studies show a direct association between prenatal exposure to environmental toxins and HSK anomalies, the contribution of environmental exposure as a possible etiology cannot be ruled out ⁽⁶⁾.

The development of HSK could instead be due to the disruption of certain signals that establish the embryonic midline during the third week of development. Among these, the Sonic Hedgehog (SHH) gene plays an important role in regulating kidney position. Another gene associated with the development of urogenital anomalies is the Wilms tumor 1 (WT1) gene; it is possible that WT1 mutations are responsible for other HSK variants ⁽⁷⁾.

There is a male predominance with a 2:1 male-to-female ratio, and up to one-third of patients with HSK remain asymptomatic until adulthood. However, these patients frequently develop renal and extrarenal complications. Renal complications include ureteropelvic junction obstruction, infection, calculi, and cancer, while extrarenal diseases and syndromes include gastrointestinal tract diseases, vertebral anomalies, and genetic disorders ^(8,9). Down syndrome has an incidence of less than 1%, while Turner syndrome occurs in 14% to 20% of cases, and Edwards syndrome is observed in up to two-thirds of cases ⁽¹⁰⁾.

Renal trauma accounts for 1% to 5% of all traumatic injuries, with an annual incidence of approximately 4.9 cases per 100,000 inhabitants; the most affected population is men with a mean age between 20 and 30 years ⁽¹¹⁾. The most common mechanism of injury affecting the kidney is blunt abdominal trauma associated with high-velocity deceleration, responsible for up to 95% of cases, while penetrating mechanisms (gunshot or stab wounds) occur in less than 4% ^(12, 13). Although the kidneys are well-protected in the retroperitoneum, they are vulnerable to blunt trauma secondary to high-velocity deceleration, such as in falls, physical assaults, contact sports, and/or traffic accidents ⁽¹²⁾. In kidneys with pre-existing abnormalities (PERL), blunt trauma accounts for up to 22% of all traumatic renal injuries and should be suspected when the injury is isolated and caused by a low-velocity mechanism ⁽¹⁴⁻¹⁸⁾. The unique anatomy of the horseshoe kidney increases its vulnerability to blunt abdominal trauma, and a proper diagnostic approach is essential for choosing the appropriate definitive treatment.

CLINICAL CASE

The patient is a 30-year-old mixed-race male, employed as an electrician, with no significant family medical history. He reported frequent use of tobacco, alcohol, marijuana, and methamphetamines since age 14, with no prior urinary symptoms. The current condition began after being struck by a motor vehicle; the kinematics of the trauma were unknown. Upon arrival at the emergency department, he presented with loss of consciousness and the following vital signs: blood pressure 110/70 mmHg, heart rate 90 beats per minute, and 99% oxygen saturation. Physical examination revealed no

cardiopulmonary compromise, an abdomen without signs of peritoneal irritation, but with lacerations on the right and left flanks; extremities were unremarkable.

Approach followed the Advanced Trauma Life Support (ATLS) guidelines. A Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) was performed, reporting negative results in all four quadrants. Laboratory tests documented hemoglobin of 12.5 g/dL, leukocytosis of 18.1 (predominantly neutrophils), creatinine of 0.94 mg/dL, urea of 25 mg/dL, and blood urea nitrogen (BUN) of 12.2 mg/dL. CT scans of the head, chest, abdomen, and pelvis were requested. Findings revealed renal units fused at the lower pole, consistent with a horseshoe kidney, showing adequate contrast enhancement. A laceration of the right renal parenchyma was observed with apparent extension into the collecting system, along with a perirenal hematoma at the superior pole and apparent contrast extravasation. The left kidney showed a laceration of approximately 2 cm without disruption of the collecting system or contrast leakage. The fusion isthmus showed no apparent lesions. Both ureters (right and left) were independent, non-dilated, without calculi, and showed adequate contrast passage. The bladder wall was intact but contained heterogeneous material suggestive of intravesical clots. A transurethral catheter was placed due to acute urinary retention, revealing gross hematuria without clot formation.

Based on clinical and tomographic findings, the injury was classified as WSES Grade III renal trauma (Grade IV right renal trauma + Grade III left renal trauma per AAST-OIS, with hemodynamic stability) ⁽¹³⁾. Initial non-operative management was chosen, based on monitoring and serial hemoglobin checks, which remained stable for 24 hours. However, the patient suffered a sudden drop in hemoglobin to 6.2 g/dL, accompanied by tachycardia (120 bpm) and a decrease in blood pressure (90/50 mmHg), showing only a transient response to resuscitation with packed red blood cells. A follow-up CT scan showed contrast extravasation at the lower pole of the right renal unit and abundant free fluid of heterogeneous density in the retroperitoneum.

An exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperative findings confirmed a horseshoe kidney with an isthmus at the lower pole, an L-shaped renal ectopia of the right kidney, and Eisendrath Type I vasculature. An expanding retroperitoneal hematoma of approximately 500 ml was found in Zones I and II. The right kidney presented full-thickness parenchymal fractures at three sites extending into the collecting systems. The fusion isthmus also showed a parenchymal fracture. The left kidney had a 3 cm laceration at the superior pole without involving the collecting system. The classification was updated to WSES Grade IV (Grade IV right renal trauma + Grade III left renal trauma per AAST-OIS, with hemodynamic instability).

The procedure included drainage of the retroperitoneal hematoma, a right simple nephrectomy, and a left nephrorrhaphy. The surgery was completed without

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complications. Postoperatively, the patient remained hospitalized under strict surveillance, including quantification of surgical site drainage and urine output, wound care, pharmacological and mechanical thromboprophylaxis, and monitoring of biochemical parameters (nitrogenous wastes, white blood cell count, and hemoglobin). The only notable finding was a creatinine

elevation to 1.56 mg/dL. Following a favorable recovery, the patient was discharged four days after surgery.

During outpatient follow-up, the histopathology report confirmed renal parenchyma with subcapsular hematoma, acute congestion, and extensive recent hemorrhage. Follow-up laboratory results showed a normalization of creatinine to 1.10 mg/dL. The patient was referred to nephrology for the management and monitoring of a solitary kidney.

Figure 1. Axial-projection computed tomography, arterial phase. A horseshoe kidney is observed with no radiological evidence of traumatic renal injury at this level.

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Figure 2. Axial-projection computed tomography, excretory phase. No contrast medium extravasation is observed at this level.

Figures 3 and 4. Axial-projection computed tomography, arterial phase. Figure 3 shows a full-thickness laceration of the renal parenchyma with apparent involvement of the collecting systems. In Figure 4, at a lower level than the previous image, a perirenal hematoma is clearly visualized at the superior pole.

Figure 5. Coronal-projection computed tomography, arterial phase. A renal parenchymal laceration is observed at the inferior pole, with a perirenal hematoma at the superior pole and a distended bladder showing an image suggestive of an intravesical clot. No traumatic injuries are observed in the liver or other organs of the abdominal cavity.

Figure 6. Coronal-projection computed tomography, excretory phase. Contrast medium extravasation is visualized at the level of the inferior pole of the renal unit.

Figures 7 and 8. Axial and coronal-projection computed tomography (respectively), excretory phase. This CT scan was performed 24 hours after admission, while the patient was experiencing hemodynamic instability with a transient response to resuscitation with packed red blood cells; a retroperitoneal hematoma larger than 3.5 cm and the "blush sign" are observed.

Figure 9. Specimen from simple right nephrectomy. The right kidney is observed with the previously described lacerations. One artery, one vein, and one ureter are visible.

Figure 10. Nephrorrhaphy of the fusion isthmus.

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Figure 11. Three-centimeter laceration at the superior renal pole. A two-layer nephrorrhaphy is performed using 2-0 polyglactin 91

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INFORMED CONSENT

Prior to data collection and the preparation of this document, the patient (SNS) was contacted by telephone. He reported no complications during his postoperative recovery. It was explained to him that, in the context of a patient with traumatic renal injury in a horseshoe kidney, there is limited literature dictating the ideal management when endovascular intervention is not an available option. Therefore, this case report will contribute to the understanding of the clinical implications and serve as a guide for future work regarding this rare but highly complex association. The patient consented and stated he has no conflict of interest.

In accordance with Mexico's General Health Law (LGS) and its secondary regulations—such as NOM-004-SSA3-2012 regarding Clinical Records and the LGS Regulation on Health Research Matters—*informed consent is mandatory for any medical act or human research, including the publication of case reports. These regulations ensure that the patient is not only informed of the study's purpose but also that the principles of autonomy, confidentiality, and privacy are respected, including the right to revoke participation in the project at any time.*

DISCUSSION

We present a case of a patient with blunt abdominal trauma where tomographic studies documented not only the presence of renal trauma but also a horseshoe kidney. This is an uncommon finding, although various case series have reported a prevalence of up to 22% of renal traumatic injuries occurring in patients with pre-existing renal abnormalities (PERL) ⁽¹⁴⁻¹⁸⁾.

According to the study conducted by Prieto et al. in 1992 ⁽¹⁵⁾, they observed a prevalence of 11.6% (13 cases out of 112 patients) of traumatic renal injury secondary to blunt trauma with PERL, with hydronephrosis secondary to ureteropelvic junction stenosis (41.6%) being the most common cause. Bahloul et al. in 1997 ⁽¹⁶⁾ reported a prevalence of 22% (34 cases out of 156 patients) of blunt renal trauma with PERL; renal lithiasis and ureteropelvic junction syndrome accounted for 44% and 29% of cases, respectively. Meanwhile, Schmidlin et al. in 1998 ⁽¹⁷⁾ described a prevalence of 19% (23 cases out of 120 patients), with renal ectopia being the third most common cause at 7% of cases. Giannopoulos et al. in 1999 ⁽¹⁸⁾ found a prevalence of 3.5% (24 cases out of 675 patients), with urolithiasis as the most common cause (50% of cases). In a study by Saadi et al. in 2023 ⁽¹⁴⁾, a prevalence of 18.2% was documented (37 cases out of 203 patients), with renal ectopia as the third most frequent cause (13.5%).

The reason why a kidney with a pre-existing abnormality is more susceptible to blunt trauma may be due to several factors. Specifically, in the case of horseshoe kidneys, they lie in a more medial and unprotected position within the retroperitoneum and possess a more complex vascular anatomy ^(14, 17, 19). This predisposes them to traumatic injury more frequently, even in low-impact mechanisms. Blunt

trauma to a horseshoe kidney is an unusual finding, being more common in men with an average age of 31.75 years. The classic presentation consists of gross hematuria, flank pain, and retroperitoneal bleeding or hematoma; it should be suspected when the injury results from a low-impact mechanism without injury to other intra-abdominal organs ⁽¹⁹⁻²²⁾.

In cases of blunt abdominal trauma, imaging studies are indicated when traumatic injury to the urinary tract is suspected (microscopic or gross hematuria), in cases of hypovolemic shock, clinical suspicion of intra-abdominal organ injury, or deceleration injury ⁽²³⁾. However, it is important to emphasize that the imaging modality depends on the patient's hemodynamic status.

Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (FAST) is a useful, reliable, and non-invasive method for blunt abdominal trauma as it helps identify the presence of free abdominal fluid. For renal evaluation, however, its anatomical position may lead to an underestimation of injuries (up to 30%), with a sensitivity and specificity of 22-26% and 96-100%, respectively ^(24, 25).

Computed tomography represents the gold standard for diagnosis. It helps detect the grade of renal trauma, the presence of renal anomalies, and the involvement of other intra-abdominal organs, with specificity and sensitivity greater than 90% ⁽²⁶⁻²⁸⁾. The arterial and venous phases allow for the identification of nearly all parenchymal and/or vascular injuries, and the addition of a delayed phase greater than 5 minutes (excretory or elimination phase) allows for the identification of contrast extravasation (13). This imaging modality can help identify patients with high-risk criteria for non-operative management (NOM) failure, such as focal contrast accumulation ("blush sign"), perirenal hematoma larger than 3.5 centimeters, medial laceration with urinary extravasation (posteromedial blush/medial renal laceration), and the absence of contrast in the ureter, which suggests complete disruption of the ureteropelvic junction ⁽¹³⁾. The association of moderate-to-severe trauma and at least two of these high-risk criteria carries a high rate of failure for non-operative management ^(13, 29).

The American Association for the Surgery of Trauma Organ Injury Scale (AAST-OIS) is the most widely used classification to determine the grade of renal traumatic injury; it underwent an update in 2018 (Table 1) ⁽³⁰⁾

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Table 1. 2018 Update of the American Association for the Surgery of Trauma Organ Injury Scale (AAST-OIS) for Renal Trauma.

Grade	Injury type	Description of Injury
I	Contusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On multidetector CT (MDCT), renal contusions appear as poorly defined irregular areas with sparse contrast enhancement during the venous phase, becoming isoattenuating in the delayed phase - Microscopic or gross hematuria with normal urological studies
	Hematoma	- Subcapsular hematoma; these accumulate within the renal capsule in a crescent-shaped or lenticular form without contrast enhancement
II	Hematoma	- Perirenal hematoma confined within Gerota's fascia
	Laceration	- Parenchymal laceration ≤ 1 cm in depth of the renal cortex without urinary extravasation
III	Laceration	- Parenchymal laceration > 1 cm in depth of the renal cortex without rupture of the collecting system or urinary extravasation
	Vascular	- Any injury with vascular involvement or active bleeding contained within Gerota's fascia (includes pseudoaneurysms and arteriovenous fistulas)
IV	Laceration	- Parenchymal laceration extending into the collecting system with urinary leak; or laceration of the renal pelvis; or complete disruption of the ureteropelvic junction
	Vascular	- Segmental renal vein or artery injury with active bleeding extending beyond Gerota's fascia into the retroperitoneum or peritoneum
	Infarction	- Segmental or complete renal infarction secondary to vascular thrombosis without active bleeding
V	Laceration	- Shattered kidney with loss of identifiable renal anatomy
	Vascular	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main renal artery or vein laceration or avulsion - Devitalization of the kidney with active bleeding

The World Society of Emergency Surgery (WSES) created a classification that considers not only the AAST-OIS grading (30) but also the patient's hemodynamic status (Table 2) (13)

Table 2. Renal trauma classification according to the World Society of Emergency Surgery.

	Grade WSES	AAST-OIS	Hemodynamic status
Minor	Grade I WSES	I-II	Stable
Moderate	Grade II WSES	III or segmental vascular injuries	Stable
Severe	Grade III WSES	IV or any degree of parenchymal injury with dissection or occlusion of main vessels	Stable
	Grade IV WSES	Any	Unstable

In adult patients with renal trauma, evaluating the hemodynamic status is crucial, as it helps determine whether the patient is a candidate for non-operative management (NOM) versus surgical intervention. A patient is considered hemodynamically unstable when the systolic blood pressure upon admission is < 90 mmHg with evidence of cutaneous vasoconstriction (coolness, decreased capillary refill, diaphoresis), altered mental status, or dyspnea; or if the blood pressure is > 90 mmHg but requires bolus infusions, transfusions, or vasopressor support. Other criteria include a base excess at admission > -5 mmol/L, a shock index > 1, or a transfusion requirement of at least 4 to 6 units of packed red blood cells within the first 24 hours (13).

Comprehensive management of renal trauma should follow a stepwise approach if circumstances permit, beginning with conservative management (NOM), followed by minimally invasive techniques (endoscopic or angiographic), and considering more radical management only if these fail. While there are no specific guidelines strictly for NOM in

blunt and penetrating trauma, its use has become increasingly popular even for high-grade renal injuries (31). However, NOM for severe injuries should only be considered in cases where close clinical observation and hemodynamic monitoring can be performed in an intermediate or intensive care unit. This must include serial clinical examinations and laboratory tests, immediate access to imaging, interventional radiology, and surgery, as well as the immediate availability of blood and blood products (13). NOM leads to higher renal preservation rates, shorter hospital stays, and complication rates comparable to operative management (OM) (32, 33).

Indications for minimally invasive surgical management via angiography and subsequent angioembolization include contrast medium extravasation on CT in hemodynamically stable patients or transient responders (34, 35), non-self-limiting gross hematuria (36), arteriovenous fistula (37), pseudoaneurysm (38), extensive perirenal hematoma (39), and a progressive decrease in hemoglobin during NOM (13). Indications for open surgical procedures (OM) include

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hemorrhage with renal pedicle avulsion, a pulsating or expanding retroperitoneal hematoma, or renal vein injury without self-limiting hemorrhage; options include partial or total nephrectomy or nephrorrhaphy^(13, 20).

Indications for surgical management in renal trauma associated with a horseshoe kidney are based on the patient's hemodynamic status (Grade III or IV shock based on ATLS) that does not respond to fluids or blood components in the presence of underlying renal pathology. Current trends favor the most conservative approach possible, even for high-grade injuries with hemodynamic stability, which can be managed conservatively in up to 90% of cases with a nephrectomy rate of only 4.6% to 5.4%^(19, 29, 40). Thus, non-operative management is considered the gold standard⁽¹⁴⁾. If surgical management is considered, minimally invasive options should always be prioritized; therefore, angiography and selective embolization are alternatives for active bleeding, with success rates of up to 98% and low complication rates, even in severe trauma or pre-existing renal disease. However, in horseshoe kidneys, the complex and abnormal vasculature presents an additional challenge for endovascular management. Open surgery should always be the last resort when both NOM and minimally invasive techniques have failed.

Among our hospital's limitations, it should be noted that as a high-volume center for blunt abdominal and other types of trauma, there is no specialized area exclusive to proper non-operative management as described in the literature. Furthermore, interventional radiology and endovascular angiology services are unavailable, making it difficult to opt for minimally invasive management. In this specific patient's case, although NOM was initially chosen, the clinical course turned unfavorable as he developed significant expansion of the retroperitoneal hematoma and a drop in hemoglobin leading to hemodynamic instability. For these reasons, open surgery was performed with the described findings. Despite these limitations, the patient experienced a favorable recovery.

CONCLUSION

In the context of blunt renal trauma with a pre-existing renal abnormality, several considerations must be taken into account. First, the diagnosis of the pre-existing abnormality is often made at the same time the renal trauma is identified, and such injuries can occur even in cases of minor trauma. The prevalence of renal trauma in patients with horseshoe kidneys is limited due to the low prevalence of this specific anomaly. Therefore, accurate radiological diagnosis and appropriate clinical surveillance are paramount when making the correct therapeutic decision. Non-operative management and endovascular intervention, when necessary, should always be the first lines of treatment, as they have been associated with low rates of nephrectomy and complications. However, open surgical management should never be ruled out when other interventions have failed.

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